

Managing Threats to Internal Validity in Quantitative and Qualitative Research: Some Basic Considerations

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Abstract

The main thrust of the paper was to examine factors that can pose threat to internal validity in both Qualitative and Quantitative research. In order to accomplish this task, the concept of validity and its various types such as content, construct and criterion-related validity were analyzed. The paper also highlighted some factors to be considered in order to achieve internal validity in both quantitative and qualitative research methods namely Maturation, Testing, Instrumentation and History among others. Although the paper acknowledged impossibility of eliminating totally the threats to internal validity especially when research is conducted outside the laboratory setting; it is the position of the paper that, good understanding and knowledge of the threats or factors that can jeopardize internal validity as highlighted in this paper can help to mitigate those threats to a minimum level and enhance the quality of the instruments and of course findings. On the basis of this conclusion, the paper suggested among other things on the need to consider the time of experiment, the use of a control group, selected from the same population as the experimental group and which experiences the same concurrent history as the experimental group are very important strategies for reducing threats to internal validity.

Keyword: Validity, Internal validity, Validity of measurement and experimental validity

Introduction

As a scientific activity, research is a search for knowledge which is embarked upon to come with findings leading to answer to question (s), development of theory or solution to a problem. For this reason, Alarape, (2012) Research is manipulations of things, concept or symbol for the purpose of generalizing extend, correct or verify knowledge, whether that knowledge aids in construction of theory or in the practice of an art. In research, information is collected to verify and generalize findings through the use of designs and various different measuring instruments namely: Questionnaire, Interview and observation among others. However, the quality of the findings and inferences made is affected by certain psychometric qualities and Validity is one of the important qualities that a good measuring instrument (test, questionnaire, observation) must possess. In line with this, Singh, (2014) noted that Validity and reliability increase transparency, and decrease opportunities to insert researcher bias in qualitative research.

The concept of Validity which is of interest to this paper is of different types and it can be applied to two areas of research: validity of measurement and validity of findings. The former, deals with those types of validity such as content validity and construct validity that are concerned with the measuring instruments, while the latter, has to do with internal and external validity of the research design. It is often associated with the experimental designs where the researcher often manipulates one variable (independent) to see its' effects on another variable (dependent).

However, one pertinent question to ask is; can the researcher confidently attribute the observed changes or differences in the dependent variable to the independent variable? This question raises the issue of internal validity. Establishing this type of validity in research serves as a herculean task to especially novice researchers. In view of this, Zainal (2017) asserts that novice researchers often face challenges such as management of extraneous variables, maintaining treatment fidelity and limited resources in an attempt to establish internal validity in research. These and other factors have to be kept under control because it is only when they properly managed can the researcher attribute the cause and effect of one variable to another. Sharma (2019) acknowledged the gravity of the threats of internal validity in survey which according to him is associated with challenges such as inadequate research design, insufficient pilot testing as well as measurement errors and biases.

The challenges of establishing internal validity are even more enormous in Qualitative research which is the method favoured by Subjectivists (naturalists) in the study of human behavior. In sociological research, these problems and many others raise the question of credibility which is concerned with the truthfulness of the research findings or how well the researcher has established confidence in research based on the method used. Indeed, according to Lawal & Ladan (2023) the Positivists (Quantitative research method) who are the antagonist of Subjectivists (Qualitative research method), pointed out that because Qualitative as a research method deals with subjective assessment of the phenomena being study in natural setting, achieving internal validity or credibility is difficult if not impossible.

Therefore, against the background of difficulties and threats in establishing internal validity in both Qualitative and Quantitative research, this paper among other issues highlighted certain basic considerations in managing the threats to the internal validity.

Conceptual Clarification

The concepts of Qualitative and Quantitative research as well as the concept of Validity are central in this discussion and thus explained.

Qualitative Research

Qualitative research is concerned with subjective assessment of attitudes, opinions and behavior. Research in such situations is a function of researcher's insight and impressions. It generates results either in non-quantifiable form or in the form which are not subjected to rigorous quantitative analysis. In other words, data is not necessarily expressed in numbers; rather it is presented in form of words. As noted by Okeshola cited in Lawal & Ladan (2023) Qualitative research uses unreconstructed logic to get at what is really real-quality, meaning, context or image of reality in what people actually do, not what they say they do. In addition, qualitative research according to Denzin and Lincoln (2014) implies an emphasis on the qualities of entities and on processes and meanings that are not experimentally examined or measured (if measured at all) in terms of quantity, amount, intensity, or frequency.

Quantitative Research

Quantitative research involves generation of data in quantitative form which can be subjected to rigorous statistical analysis. It entails the collection of data in numbers. Obasi cited in Lawal & Ladan (2023) defined quantitative research as an aspect of the scientific method that investigates phenomena that are amenable to empirical measurement and verification. This means examining variables that can be assigned figures or values which can be empirically observed. The Quantitative procedure of assigning figures is different from Qualitative research which deals with detail description of phenomena being studied.

Validity

Validity is an important determinant of the quality of any measuring instrument. A review of various definitions of Validity from different literatures reveals that the concept of validity is defined by different authors in almost similar perspectives. For example, Kauru (2015) defines Validity as the degree to which the tool measures what it claims to measure while Kamar (2017) stated that, validity means the accuracy with which a test measures what it intends to or supposed to measure. Similarly, Validity can also refer to the ability of measuring instrument to measure truly and accurately the quality or ability it is designed to measure. In other words, a measuring instrument is said to be valid, when it measures truly and accurately the quality or ability it is designed to measure. This means that a test that is designed to test achievement should do just that and nothing else. Middleton (2023) explained that Validity along with Reliability are the two concepts that are utilized to measure the quality of research. Validity in research therefore deals with the extent to which research instrument measure what it is supposed to measure. Thus, one important thing clear from the above definitions is that, the concept of validity is defined in relation to measuring tool, instrument or test. However, validity can also be defined or viewed in relation to Research Design. For instance, according to Asika cited in Lawal and Ladan (2023), a research design may be said to be valid if it enables a researcher to elicit the correct responses from the sample subjects, otherwise it can be regarded as faulty design and may not lead to correct outcomes.

There are different types of validity which can be applied to different areas of research. It is in line with this that Asika cited in Lawal and Ladan (2023), maintained that, the concept of validity can be applied in two areas of research: validity of measurement and validity of findings or experimental validity. Validity of measurement is ability of the measuring instrument to measure what it is supposed to measure. In relation to this, Kamar (2017) observed that there are three major types of validity that are commonly used in educational and psychological measurements. These are namely: Content Validity, Criterion-related validity and Construct validity.

Content validity: this type of Validity emphasized on adequate coverage of the scope of the topic. Kauru (2015) observes that content validity involves the systematic examination of the test content to determine whether it covers a representative sample of the behavior domain to be measured content validity is therefore directed to the following questions:

1. Have all the relevant dimensions of the topic been fully explored?
2. Does the measuring instrument adequately cover all the dimensions or at least a good representation of all the dimensions of the topic of research?

These questions must to be answered for an instrument to possess content validity. In line with this, Asika cited in Lawal and Ladan (2023), explains that content validity can be determined by the designer of the instrument in any of the following ways:

- i. By ensuring that all the questions asked in the instrument questionnaire fully exhaust all that are implied by the research questions and hypotheses.
- ii. By using a panel of judges who would vet the questions in the questionnaire objectively, paying particular attention to their relevance to the subject matter and their coverage the entire topic of the study.

Criterion-related validity

Criterion-related validity involves comparing the test with other test(s) (criterion) that is held to be valid. Some instruments or tests are known or have been determined to be good measures of certain variables or attribute. Such test otherwise known as criterion can be used as basis for judging the validity of a newly designed instrument. For example, some of the West African Examination (WAEC) Examinations have been determined over time to be good measures of the candidate's intelligence. If a researcher is to design his own instrument to equally measure the students' intelligence, how does his own instrument compare or relate to a similar established criterion that is the WAEC examinations?

Criterion related validity is of two types: the predictive and concurrent validity. Predictive validity measures how the newly designed measuring instrument adequately predicts certain attributes it is designed to measure while the concurrent validity measures how the newly designed measuring instrument measures other current behaviors or variables.

Construct validity

The word construct according to Salawu & Kamar (2017) is a high-level concept that has been invented for particular purpose. Examples of construct are the terms motivation and intelligence. Motivation is used to explain human behavior and intelligence is used to study difference in human learning or human behavior. Construct validity is therefore an attempt to measure how adequately an instrument measures the actual meaning of a construct. Gay, Mills and Airasian (2022) opined that, construct validity attempts to explain whether the test reflects the actual meaning of the construct or not. For instance, how well results from a test on stress reflect the actual theoretical characteristics of stress is a measure of construct validity. However, there are other types of validity.

Experimental validity or Validity of Findings

This type validity is associated with Experimental research. Best & Kahn (2016) stated that Conventional experiment usually involves two groups: Experimental group and Control group and experimental group is exposed to influence of the factor under consideration. Observations are then made to determine what difference appears or what changes or modifications occur in the experimental group as contrasted with the control group. Experimental validity or Validity of findings therefore refers to the problem of the adequacy of a research design in eliciting the type of responses that it is designed to generate. In other words, a research design may be said to be valid if it enables a researcher elicit the correct responses from the sample subjects, otherwise it is a faulty design and may not lead to correct findings. In relation to this, there are two (2) types of validity. They are namely: External validity and internal validity.

External Validity

External validity refers to the degree to which it is warranted to generalize results to other contexts. External validity asks questions of generalization. To what population, setting can the effects observed be generalized. Best & Kahn (2016) stated that the researcher would achieve little of practical value if these observed variable valid only in the experimental setting and only for those participating. External validity is therefore extent to which the variable relationship can be generalized to other setting, other treatment variables, other measurement variables and other population.

Internal Validity

Internal Validity is concerned with the extent to which a causal conclusion based on a study is warranted, which is determined by the degree to which a study minimizes systematic error (or bias). An experiment is said to have internal validity if the factors that have been manipulated (independent variables) actually have genuine effect on the observed consequences or dependent variable. For example, consider the following outcomes of an experiment of two separate teaching methods;

Pre-test mean score (Mean Score before the treatment) = 20 %

Post-test Mean Score (Mean Score after the treatment) = 60%

In this example, the researcher wants to make a causal inference that 40% difference is caused only by the treatment that is the teaching method. In other words, when the researcher may confidently attribute the observed changes or differences

in the dependent variable to the independent variable, and when the researcher can rule out other explanations then the causal inference is said to be internally valid.

Internal Validity in Qualitative Research Method

Qualitative research is a method that is more frequently adopted in social science disciplines. While, Quantitative research involves generation of data in quantitative form which can be subjected to rigorous statistical analysis, Qualitative however employs few if any quantitative data gathering instruments. It uses unstructured and semi-structured methods such as in-depth interviews, focus groups, and participant observation for data collection.

In qualitative research method, the word Credibility is used to refer to internal validity. Credibility is concerned with how well the researcher has established confidence in research based on the research design. Mahuta (2016) stated that credibility is concerned with the truthfulness of the research findings. Since qualitative research method deals with subjective assessment of the phenomena being study in natural setting, its critics (positivist) are of the opinion that achieving internal validity or credibility is difficult if not impossible in qualitative research method. However, Donald, Lucy & Chris cited in Mahuta (2016) stated that credibility (internal validity) in qualitative research can be enhanced through the following methods:

1. Structural corroboration which has to do with Data triangulation.
2. Consensus which has to do with Investigator triangulation
3. Control of bias which can be done through reflexivity or use of self-reflection to recognize one's own biases and to actively seek them out.

Basic Consideration for Achieving Internal Validity

In many cases, the magnitude of effects found in the dependent variable may not just depend on independent variable, there are certain factors or variable that could exert some influence over the dependent variable which serves as threats to internal validity. They are extraneous variables or circumstances that if not well control can affect the internal validity. These factors include: Maturation, testing, instrumentation, differential selection of subjects, experimental mortality, statistical regression, Hawthorn effects among other factors. Some of these factors are explained below:

- i. **Maturation:** The subject being measured may change during the course of the experiment or even between measurements which may be due to psychological and physical changes. For example, consider this experiment on methods of teaching
Group I (experimental) given treatment from 8:00am– 9:00 am
Group II (control) given treatment from 1:00pm – 2: 00 pm
Any outcome obtained from this experiment cannot serve as a basis for comparison. Physical and psychological changes may put the control group at the disadvantage. The afternoon time may be too hot. Similarly, the control group may get tired, bored and loss interest or eager to go home.
- ii. **Testing:** the testing itself may sensitize the subjects being tested or measured (found in pre-test post-test). If the same test is used for pre and post-tests, the possibility is that the subjects have mastered the former to help their performance in the second. In other words, Best & Kahn (2016) stated that pre-testing may produce a practice effect that may make subjects more proficient in subsequent test performance.
- iii. **Instrumentation:** Unreliable instruments used to describe and measure aspects of behavior are threat to internal validity of an experiment. For instance, an instrument of observation that is not reliable, a serious element of error is introduced. Similarly, if human observers are used to describe behavior changes in subjects, changes in observers or in their standards due to fatigue, increased in sight or skill or changes in criteria of judgment over period of time are likely to introduce error. With regards to test as instrument Essay type of tests especially, Salawu & Kamar (2017) pointed out that if the pre-test and post-test are marked by different scorers there will be contradiction to validity. Whether or not marking schemes are provided for the separate scorers or assessors, element of bias is already introduced.
- iv. **History:** History in this context refers to specific random events, which are beyond the control of the researcher that can affect the performance of the subjects. Such events can occur between the first and second measurement. Take for example an experiment which takes 5 – 10 weeks in a school setting. Some of the students may go beyond the lectures (treatment) being given, thus having extra experience during the interval between pre and posts test. This is beyond the control of the researcher but can have effect on the performance of the subjects.
- v. **Experimental Mortality:** this is loss of subjects from the sample due to resignations, apathy or death. It may likely to occur in the long-term experiment and error can occur if inferences are made on the basis of only those participants that have participated from the start to the end. For example, an experiment was started with 30 samples but at the end

only 20 or less are left to continue, then there is experimental mortality because some of those 10 or more students who left may be special students or those with low marks.

- vi. **Statistical Regression:** Subjects, who score highest in the pre-test, may score lower on the re-test; subjects who score higher on pre-test may score high on re-test. Scores at the extreme tend to go towards the mean. In other words, this type of error occurs when subjects are selected on the basis of extreme scores (one far away from the mean) during a test. For example, when children with the worst reading scores are selected to participate in a reading course, improvements at the end of the course might be due to regression toward the mean and not the course's effectiveness. If the children had been tested again before the course started, they would likely have obtained better scores anyway. For example, consider this experiment, a situation where after teaching with two methods, a teacher ranks students according to marks:
Group A 1 – 30 %
Group B 71- 100 %
This comparison makes it impossible to actually find out the effect of one variable on the other because only the best performing (71- 100 %) and worst performing (1 – 30 %) were selected. The subjects are not true representation of the population. In this case, the researcher should not pick from the two extremes.
- vii. **Selection Bias:** this is bias in the selection of students or other groups of people for an experimental research study. This may render deductions from such exercises worthless.
- viii. **Experimenter Bias:** This factor as explained by Best & Kahn (2016) is a type of bias introduced when the researcher has some previous knowledge about the subjects involved in an experiment. This knowledge of subject status may cause the researcher to convey some clue that affect the subject's reaction or may affect the objectivity of his or her judgment.

Conclusion

Many threats to internal validity of especially experiment are difficult to be eliminated totally particularly when research is conducted outside the laboratory setting; where there are many extraneous variables to control. However, knowledge of the threats or factors that can jeopardize it is crucial. It enables the researcher to mitigate those threats to a minimum level and enhance the quality of the instruments and of course findings.

Recommendations

Threat to internal validity is inevitable challenge more especially in Experimental research design. However, the following suggestions can minimize those threats and enable researcher confidently attributes the observed changes or differences in the dependent variable to the independent variable:

1. To reduce the threats generated by History & Maturation, there is need to consider the time of experiment. In order words, the shorter the duration of an experiment, the less likely that maturation will occur. Similarly, the use of a control group, selected from the same population as the experimental group and which experiences the same concurrent history as the experimental group is another strategy for reducing threats to internal validity.
2. With regards to testing, many actions can be taken to ensure that the possibility of proficiency as a result of the mastery of pre-test is checkmated. Among which are, the use of a research design that does not include a pretest. Even where the experiment involved pre-test, the use of different but equivalent forms of a test for pre-test and post-test is another option.
3. Random sampling and random assignment of subjects are some of the viable ways to reduce threats arising from bias in selection. Where random sampling and assignment are not possible, statistical techniques such as ANCOVA can be utilized to adjust for group differences. Similarly, researchers should desist from being bias or subjective in scoring the instruments, objectivity is therefore essential as far as internal validity is concerned.
4. Standardized instruments possessed the quality of reliability. To eliminate instrumentation threats therefore, there is need for the researchers to adopt or adapt standardized instruments more especially in situations whereby the reliability of the researcher-designed instruments cannot be ascertained. In addition, careful specification and control of the measurement procedures as well as the training of study personnel are among other procedures that help control the instrumentation threat.
5. Researchers also need avoid assigning subjects to groups based on their extreme scores in order to prevent the internal validity threats arising from statistical regression.

6. Some circumstances leading to experimental mortality such as death is unavoidable but other conditions such as anger, apathy, and frustration can be managed. There is therefore need for the researchers to provide enabling conditions that can encourage participants to willingly and objectivity participate in the experiment from the start to the completion. Other basic considerations are: the use of single scorers or markers on issue of instrumentation, avoiding picking from two extreme scores to check statistical regression, randomization among others. Similarly, pure or true experimental design enable researcher to neutralize the threat or influence of both internal and external validity.

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